

EchinoDB (v2.0) code

```
library(shiny)
library(shinydashboard)
library(RPostgreSQL)
library(pool)
library(DBI)
library(DT)
library(formattable)
library(shinyWidgets)
library(seqinr)
library(shinyjs)

customGreen0 = "#ffffff"
customGreen = "#219f9c"
customBlue = "#337ab7"

setMethod("dbQuoteLiteral", c("Pool", "ANY"),
  function(conn, x, ...) {
    # As of 2020-05-07, this is necessary due to an incompatibility
    # between packages `pool` (v 0.1.4.3) and `glue` (v >= 1.3.2).
    connection <- pool::poolCheckout(conn)
    on.exit(pool::poolReturn(connection))
    DBI::dbQuoteLiteral(connection, x, ...)
  }
)
# Loop through outp dataframe to extract reference seq id
# myfunc <- function(x){
#   y <- x[3]
#   s = gregexpr(pattern = 'XP_', y)
#   st <- s[[1]][1]
#   n<- nchar(y)
#   x[4] <- noquote(substring(y, st, n-1))
# }

concat <- function(x){
  aa <- x[1]
  bj <- x[2]
  sp <- x[3]
  y <- paste0(sp, ', anum:', aa, ', bnum:', bj)
  y
}

proper <- function(x) {
  x <- tolower(x)
  substr(x, 1, 1) <- toupper(substr(x, 1, 1))
  x
}
```

```

jscode <- '$(document).keyup(function(e) {
  if (e.key == "Enter") {
    $("#searchButton").click();
  }});'

jsDeleteKey <- '$(document).keyup(function(e) {
  if (e.key == "Delete") {
    $("#clearButton").click();
  }});'

#jsBackSpaceKey <- '$(document).keyup(function(e) {
# if (e.key == "Backspace") {
#   $("#clearButton").click();
# }});'

jsRefresh <- 'shinyjs.refresh = function(){
  history.go(0);
}'

jsURL <- "
shinyjs.browseURL = function(url) {
  window.open(url,'_blank');
}
"

# Define UI for application
ui <- dashboardPage(
  dashboardHeader(title = "Echinodb", tags$li(class = "dropdown", actionLink(inputId="ss", label="Link
to BLAST Sequence Server",
    class = "ss_class", icon = icon("send"), onclick
="window.open('https://echinodb.uncc.edu/sequenceserver/')")),
  dashboardSidebar(
    tags$head(tags$style(HTML(".checkbox {margin: 0}
.checkbox p {margin: 0;} .shiny-input-container {margin-bottom: 0;} "))),
    tags$head(tags$style(HTML("#BriOptions,#ForciOptions,#NotoOptions,#PaxOptions,
#SriOptions,#ValOptions,#VelOptions,#ComOptions,#HyoOptions,#ArbOptions,
#CidOptions,#ClyOptions,#EchOptions,#ApoOptions,#AspOptions,#DenOptions,
#DendOptions,#ElasOptions,#MolOptions,#EurOptions,#GnaOptions,#OphOptions,#OphiOptions
{padding-top: 5px !important;border-color: #ffffff;border-style: dotted;color:#2E4053;background-
color:#FBFCFC;}"))),

    tags$head(tags$script(HTML(jscode))),
    tags$head(tags$script(HTML(jsDeleteKey))),
    #tags$head(tags$script(HTML(jsBackSpaceKey))),

    textInput(inputId = "searchText",placeholder = "gene name, keywords, etc.", label = "Enter Keyword &
Hit Enter"),
    actionButton(inputId = "searchButton", label="Submit Search",icon("search"),

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        style="color: #fff; background-color: #a4163e; border-color:#a4163e;"),
    actionButton(inputId = "clearButton", label="Clear", icon("backspace"),
        style="color: #ffffff; background-color: #006680;border-color:#006680;"),

    prettySwitch(inputId = "allSwitch",label = "Selection of Taxa",fill = TRUE, status = "success", value =
TRUE),
    conditionalPanel(
        condition="input.allSwitch!=1",
        prettySwitch(inputId = "ASwitch",label = "Asteroidea",fill = TRUE, status = "info", value = TRUE),

        conditionalPanel(
            condition="input.ASwitch==1",
            checkboxGroupInput("Aoptions","Asteroidea:",
                choices=c("Brisingida",
"Forcipulatida","Notomyotida","Paxillosida","Spinulosida","Valvatida","Velatida"),
                selected=c("Brisingida",
"Forcipulatida","Notomyotida","Paxillosida","Spinulosida","Valvatida","Velatida")
            ),
            conditionalPanel("input.Aoptions.indexOf('Brisingida') > -1",
                checkboxGroupInput("BriOptions", "Brisingida",
                    choices=c("Brisingidae"),
                    selected= c("Brisingidae"))
            ),
            conditionalPanel("input.Aoptions.indexOf('Forcipulatida') > -1",
                checkboxGroupInput("ForciOptions", "Forcipulatida:",
                    choices = c("Asteroiidae", "Labidiasteridae"),
                    selected = c("Asteroiidae", "Labidiasteridae"))
            ),
            conditionalPanel(condition="input.Aoptions.indexOf('Notomyotida') > -1",
                checkboxGroupInput("NotoOptions", "Notomyotida:",
                    choices = c("Benthopectinidae"),
                    selected=c("Benthopectinidae"))
            ),
            conditionalPanel(condition="input.Aoptions.indexOf('Paxillosida') > -1",
                checkboxGroupInput("PaxOptions", "Paxillosida:",
                    choices = c("Astropectinidae", "Luidiidae"),
                    selected = c("Astropectinidae", "Luidiidae"))
            ),
            conditionalPanel("input.Aoptions.indexOf('Spinulosida') > -1",
                checkboxGroupInput("SriOptions", "Spinulosida:",
                    choices=c("Echinasteridae"),
                    selected= c("Echinasteridae"))
            ),
            conditionalPanel(condition="input.Aoptions.indexOf('Valvatida') > -1",
                checkboxGroupInput("ValOptions", "Valvatida:",
                    choices = c("Asteropectinidae", "Poraniidae", "Solasteridae"),
                    selected = c("Asteropectinidae", "Poraniidae", "Solasteridae"))
            ),
        ),
    ),

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conditionalPanel(condition="input.Aoptions.indexOf('Velatida') > -1",
  checkboxGroupInput("VelOptions", "Velatida:",
    choices = c("Korethrasteridae", "Pterasteridae", "Xyloplacidae"),
    selected = c("Korethrasteridae", "Pterasteridae", "Xyloplacidae"))
)
),
# Crinoidea Species and its order and family
prettySwitch(inputId = "CSwitch",label = "Crinoidea",
  fill = TRUE, status = "info", value = TRUE),
conditionalPanel(
  condition="input.CSwitch==1",
  checkboxGroupInput("Coptions","Crinoidea:",
    choices=c("Comatulida", "Hyocrinida"),
    selected=c("Comatulida", "Hyocrinida")
),
conditionalPanel("input.Coptions.indexOf('Comatulida') > -1",
  checkboxGroupInput("ComOptions", "Comatulida:",
    choices=c("Antedonidae", "Bourgueticrinidae", "Colobometridae",
"Comasteridae","Ptilometridae","Zenometridae"),
    selected= c("Antedonidae", "Bourgueticrinidae", "Colobometridae",
"Comasteridae","Ptilometridae","Zenometridae"))
),
conditionalPanel("input.Coptions.indexOf('Hyocrinida') > -1",
  checkboxGroupInput("HyoOptions", "Hyocrinida:",
    choices=c("Hyocrinidae"),
    selected= c("Hyocrinidae"))
)
),
# Echinoidea Species and its order and family
prettySwitch(inputId = "ESwitch",label = "Echinoidea",
  fill = TRUE, status = "info", value = TRUE),
conditionalPanel(condition="input.ESwitch==1",
  checkboxGroupInput("Eoptions","Echinoidea:",
    choices=c("Arbacioida", "Cidaroida","Clypeasteroida", "Echinoida"),
    selected=c("Arbacioida", "Cidaroida","Clypeasteroida", "Echinoida")),
conditionalPanel("input.Eoptions.indexOf('Arbacioida') > -1",
  checkboxGroupInput("ArbOptions", "Arbacioida:",
    choices=c("Arbaciidae"),
    selected= c("Arbaciidae"))
),
conditionalPanel("input.Eoptions.indexOf('Cidaroida') > -1",
  checkboxGroupInput("CidOptions", "Cidaroida:",
    choices=c("Cidaridae"),
    selected= c("Cidaridae"))
),
conditionalPanel("input.Eoptions.indexOf('Clypeasteroida') > -1",
  checkboxGroupInput("ClyOptions", "Clypeasteroida:",
    choices=c("Dendrasteridae"),

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        selected= c("Dendrasteridae"))
    ),
    conditionalPanel("input.Eoptions.indexOf('Echinoida') > -1",
        checkboxGroupInput("EchOptions", "Echinoida:",
            choices=c("Strongylocentrotidae"),
            selected= c("Strongylocentrotidae"))
    )
),
# Holothuroidea Species and its order and family
prettySwitch(inputId = "HSwitch",label = "Holothuroidea",
    fill = TRUE, status = "info", value = TRUE),
conditionalPanel(
    condition="input.HSwitch==1",
    checkboxGroupInput("Hoptions","Holothuroidea:",
        choices=c("Apodida", "Aspidochirotida","Dendrochirotacea", "Dendrochirotida",
"Elasipodida", "Molpadida"),
        selected=c("Apodida", "Aspidochirotida", "Dendrochirotacea", "Dendrochirotida",
"Elasipodida", "Molpadida")
    ),
    conditionalPanel("input.Hoptions.indexOf('Apodida') > -1",
        checkboxGroupInput("ApoOptions", "Apodida:",
            choices=c("Synaptidae"),
            selected= c("Synaptidae"))
    ),
    conditionalPanel("input.Hoptions.indexOf('Aspidochirotida') > -1",
        checkboxGroupInput("AspOptions", "Aspidochirotida:",
            choices=c("Stichopodidae", "Synallactidae"),
            selected= c("Stichopodidae", "Synallactidae"))
    ),
    conditionalPanel("input.Hoptions.indexOf('Dendrochirotacea') > -1",
        checkboxGroupInput("DenOptions", "Dendrochirotacea:",
            choices=c("Cucumariidae", "Psolidae"),
            selected= c("Cucumariidae", "Psolidae"))
    ),
    conditionalPanel("input.Hoptions.indexOf('Dendrochirotida') > -1",
        checkboxGroupInput("DendOptions", "Dendrochirotida:",
            choices=c("Psolidae"),
            selected= c("Psolidae"))
    ),
    conditionalPanel("input.Hoptions.indexOf('Elasipodida') > -1",
        checkboxGroupInput("ElasOptions", "Elasipodida:",
            choices=c("Laetmogonidae"),
            selected= c("Laetmogonidae"))
    ),
    conditionalPanel("input.Hoptions.indexOf('Molpadida') > -1",
        checkboxGroupInput("MolOptions", "Molpadida:",
            choices=c("Molpadidae"),
            selected= c("Molpadidae"))
    )

```

```

)
),
# Ophiuroidea Species and its order and family
prettySwitch(inputId = "OSwitch",label = "Ophiuroidea", fill = TRUE, status = "info", value = TRUE),
conditionalPanel(
  condition="input.OSwitch==1",
  checkboxGroupInput("Ooptions","Ophiuroidea:",
    choices=c("Euryalida", "Gnathophiuridea", "Ophiocomidea", "Ophiurida"),
    selected=c("Euryalida", "Gnathophiuridea","Ophiocomidea", "Ophiurida")
  ),
  conditionalPanel("input.Ooptions.indexOf('Euryalida') > -1",
    checkboxGroupInput("EurOptions", "Euryalida:",
      choices=c("Gorgonocephalidae"),
      selected= c("Gorgonocephalidae"))
  ),
  conditionalPanel("input.Ooptions.indexOf('Gnathophiuridea') > -1",
    checkboxGroupInput("GnaOptions", "Gnathophiuridea:",
      choices=c("Ophiotrichidae"),
      selected= c("Ophiotrichidae"))
  ),
  conditionalPanel("input.Ooptions.indexOf('Ophiocomidea') > -1",
    checkboxGroupInput("OphOptions", "Ophiocomidea:",
      choices=c("Ophiocomidae"),
      selected= c("Ophiocomidae"))
  ),
  conditionalPanel("input.Ooptions.indexOf('Ophiurida') > -1",
    checkboxGroupInput("OphiOptions", "Ophiurida:",
      choices=c("Ophiodermatidae"),
      selected= c("Ophiodermatidae"))
  )
)
)
),
dashboardBody(
  shinyjs::useShinyjs(),
  shinyjs::extendShinyjs(text = jsRefresh, functions = c("refresh")),
  shinyjs::extendShinyjs(text = jsURL, functions = c("browseURL")),
  tags$head(tags$style(HTML('#searchText{color: #337ab7;border-color:orange; font-weight:bold;}')),
  tags$style(type="text/css", "#text1{ height: 250px; color: #006680; background-color:#FFFFFF; border-
color:#006680; font-weight:bold; word-wrap: break-word; white-space: normal;}"),
  tags$style(type="text/css", "#text2, #text5{color: #b20838; background-color:#FFFAFA; font-
weight:bold; border-color:#FFFAFA;}"),
  tags$style(type="text/css", "#text{ background-color: #006680; color: #ffffff; word-wrap: break-word;
display: inline-block;
overflow-wrap: break-word; word-break: normal;
line-break: strict; white-space: normal; font-family: Times New Roman;}"),
  tags$style(type="text/css", "#text4{height: 80px; color: #006680; background-color:#FFFFFF; border-
color:#006680; font-weight:bold; word-wrap: break-word; white-space: normal;}"),

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tags$style(type="text/css", "#download, #download1, #download2, #downloadDoc{color: #ffffff;
background-color:#006680;float:right; font-family: Brush Script MT, monospace;}"),
tags$style(type="text/css", "#text3{color: #b20838; background-color:#FFFAFA; font-weight:bold;
border-color:#FFFAFA;}"),
tags$style(type="text/css", "#text6{color: #2F4F4F; font-weight:bold; font-family: Brush Script MT,
monospace;float:right;}"),
tags$style(HTML(".ss_class {color: #FFFFFF; font-family: Copperplate; }")),
tags$style(type="text/css", "#downloadFile{ font-weight:bold; font-family: Brush Script MT,
monospace;float:right;}"),
tags$style(type = 'text/css', ".badge{min-width: 200px;}"),
tags$head(tags$style(HTML('.sidebar-menu>li>a{display: contents;}'))),

sidebarMenu(
  menuItem(text= NULL,
    badgeColor = "light-blue", badgeLabel = "Link to Ophioderma brevispinum transcriptome",
    href = "https://echinodb.uncc.edu/BStarApp"),
  menuItem(text= NULL, badgeColor = "maroon", badgeLabel = "Link to Lytechinus variegatus
Data",
    href = "https://echinodb.uncc.edu/SUrchinApp")
),
br(),
br(),
fluidRow(
  box(status = "danger", width=12, solidHeader = FALSE, collapsible = TRUE,
    tabsetPanel(id= "main",
      tabPanel("Results", br(), verbatimTextOutput("text3"),
        DT::dataTableOutput("table")),
      tabPanel("Orthocluster", downloadButton('download2',"Ortho
Sequences"),br(),br(),verbatimTextOutput("text2"),
        DT::dataTableOutput("table1")),
      tabPanel("Individual Sequences", br(), verbatimTextOutput("text5"),
downloadButton('download',"Protein Sequence"),br(),br(), verbatimTextOutput("text4"),
        downloadButton('download1', "DNA Sequence"), br(), br(),
verbatimTextOutput("text1")),
      tabPanel("Literature", downloadLink('downloadFile',"Click for data from Linchangco et al.
2017"),br(), br(),
        DT::dataTableOutput("papersTable")),
      tabPanel("Documentation",
        downloadButton('downloadDoc',"Download Document"),br(),br(),
        textOutput("text6"),
        DT::dataTableOutput("docsTable"))
    ),
  br(),
  verbatimTextOutput("text"),
  uiOutput("images")
)
)

```

```
)  
)
```

```
# Define server logic required to draw a histogram
```

```
server <- function(input, output, session) {  
  pool <- dbPool(  
    drv = dbDriver("PostgreSQL", max.con = 100),  
    dbname = "XXXXXX",  
    host = "XXXXXXXX",  
    user = "XXXXXXXX",  
    password = "XXXXXXXX",  
    idleTimeout = 3600000  
  )
```

```
  sqlP <- "SELECT title,link from echinopapers;"  
  queryP <- sqlInterpolate(pool,sqlP)  
  outLP <- dbGetQuery(pool, queryP)  
  outLP1 <- as.data.frame(outLP[,1])  
  colnames(outLP1) <- 'Title'
```

```
  sqlD <- "SELECT title,location, extension, contentTp from echinomanual;"  
  queryD <- sqlInterpolate(pool,sqlD)  
  outLD <- dbGetQuery(pool, queryD)  
  outLD1 <- as.data.frame(outLD[,1])  
  colnames(outLD1) <- 'Document Name'
```

```
  output$text <- renderText("EchinoDB is a database consisting of amino acid sequence orthoclusters  
from 42 echinoderm transcriptomes. We sampled taxa to span the deepest divergences within each of  
the 5 extant echinoderm classes. Data can be searched by keywords such as annotation and database  
identifiers from the Strongylocentrotus purpuratus reference protein set at NCBI.")
```

```
  output$images <- renderUI({  
    tags$div(  
      img(width= "80"),  
      img(src='EchinolImages.PNG', width="800")  
      #img(src='Starfish.png', width="120", height="90"),  
      #img(width= "15"),  
      #img(src='Echino.png', width="120", height="90")  
    )  
  })
```

```
  observeEvent(input$allSwitch, {  
    if(input$allSwitch == FALSE){  
      updatePrettySwitch(session, inputId= "ASwitch", value = FALSE)  
      updatePrettySwitch(session, inputId= "CSwitch", value = FALSE)  
      updatePrettySwitch(session, inputId= "ESwitch", value = FALSE)  
      updatePrettySwitch(session, inputId= "HSwitch", value = FALSE)  
      updatePrettySwitch(session, inputId= "OSwitch", value = FALSE)  
    } else if(input$allSwitch == TRUE){  
      updatePrettySwitch(session, inputId= "ASwitch", value = TRUE)
```

```

updatePrettySwitch(session, inputId= "CSwitch", value = TRUE)
updatePrettySwitch(session, inputId= "ESwitch", value = TRUE)
updatePrettySwitch(session, inputId= "HSwitch", value = TRUE)
updatePrettySwitch(session, inputId= "OSwitch", value = TRUE)
}}
)

observeEvent(input$searchButton, {
  req(input$searchText)
  sql <- "SELECT gi_num, rfname, otherids, refnum FROM refseqs_view WHERE ((rfname LIKE ?name OR
rfname LIKE ?name1 OR rfname LIKE ?name2) AND rfname NOT LIKE '%uncharacterized protein%') OR
(refnum LIKE ?name3);"
  query <- sqlInterpolate(pool,sql, name = noquote(paste0('%', tolower(input$searchText), '%')),
    name1 = noquote(paste0('%', toupper(input$searchText), '%')),
    name2 = noquote(paste0('%', proper(input$searchText), '%')),
    name3 = noquote(paste0('%', input$searchText, '%')))

  outp <- dbGetQuery(pool, query)
  sql= NULL
  query = NULL

  if(length(outp) > 0) {
    if(input$allSwitch == TRUE || (input$allSwitch == FALSE & input$ASwitch == TRUE & input$CSwitch
== TRUE & input$ESwitch == TRUE & input$HSwitch == TRUE & input$OSwitch == TRUE)){
      v1 <- outp[,1]
      sql <- "SELECT COUNT(*),gi_num FROM orthoclusters WHERE gi_num IN ({gi*}) GROUP BY gi_num;"
      query <- glue::glue_sql(sql, gi = v1, .con=pool)
      outp1 <- dbGetQuery(pool, query)
      sql= NULL
      query = NULL

      outp <- as.data.frame(subset(outp, outp[,1] %in% outp1[,2]))

      # Sort outp and outp1 data by gi_num
      outp <- outp[order(outp$gi_num),]
      outp1 <- outp1[order(outp1[,2]),]

      # Create new column for total hits in outp dataframe
      outp$TotalHits <- outp1[,1]

      # Clear count data from ortholuster
      outp1 = NULL
      # names(outp)[names(outp) == "_searchtext"] <- "Refseq_Id"
      # outp[,4] <- apply(outp, 1, myfunc)
      names(outp)[names(outp) == "refnum"] <- "Accession#"
      output$text3 <- renderText(paste0(nrow(outp), " result(s) found"))

      output$table <- DT::renderDataTable( {

```

```

as.datatable(
  selection = "single",
  style = 'bootstrap',
  formattable(outp, list(
    paging = TRUE, cyl = col_format(),
    `gi_num` = color_tile(customGreen, customGreen)
  )))
})

```

If row is selected, navigate to Orthocluster tab

```

observeEvent(input$table_rows_selected, {
  shiny::withProgress(message='Please wait...', detail= 'Loading data', value = 0, {
    n <- 1
    for (i in 1:n) {
      shiny::incProgress(amount=1/n)
      selectedIndex <- input$table_rows_selected
      selectedRow <- outp[selectedIndex,]
      selectedGI <- selectedRow[,1]
      selectedHit <- paste0('Orthocluster for ', selectedRow[,4], ' (',
        selectedGI, ')', '\n', selectedRow[,2], '\n',
        selectedRow[,5], ' sequences in orthocluster')

```

```

      query <- sqlInterpolate(ANSI(),
        "SELECT aanumber, bjnumber, concat(bjnumber, ':', aanumber) AS aa_bjnum,
gi_num from orthoclusters WHERE gi_num = ?gi_no;",
        gi_no = selectedGI)
      outp2 <- dbGetQuery(pool, query)
      query <- NULL

```

```

      aabj = outp2[,3]

```

```

      sql1 <- "select aanumber, bjnumber, sp_name, bio_proj_accesion, amino_sequence from
TESTDB_VIEW where aa_bjnum IN ({{aabj*}});"
      query3 <- glue::glue_sql(sql1, aabj= aabj, .con=pool)
      outp3 <- dbGetQuery(pool, query3)
      sql1 <- NULL
      query3 <- NULL
      aabj = NULL

```

Generate Header for download orthocluster sequence

```

seqs_fasta <- outp3[,5]
giID <- paste0(' id:', selectedGI, ', orthocluster:', selectedRow[,4])
namesList <- apply(outp3, 1, concat)
names_fasta <- paste(namesList, rep(giID))
namesList = NULL

```

Add space after 60 lines in a sequence

```

    outp3[,5] <- gsub('{.60}', '\\1 ', outp3[,5])

    output$text2 <- renderText(selectedHit)
  } #End of Progress Bar For Loop
})

output$table1 <- renderDataTable({
  expr = DT::datatable(outp3,
    selection="single",
    options = list(columnDefs = list(list(visible=FALSE, targets={1:2})))
  ) %>% formatStyle("amino_sequence", color = customBlue, fontWeight = 'bold')
})

output$download2 <- downloadHandler(
  filename = function() {
    paste("Ortho_Sequences-", Sys.Date(), ".fasta", sep="")
  },
  content = function(fname) {
    seqinr::write.fasta(as.list(seqs_fasta), names=names_fasta, file=fname)
  }
)
updateTabsetPanel(session, "main", selected = "Orthocluster")

# If row is selected, navigate to tab3
observeEvent(input$table1_rows_selected, {
  index <- input$table1_rows_selected
  aaNum = outp3[index,1]
  bjNum = outp3[index,2]
  amino_seq = gsub(" ", "", outp3[index,5])

  query2 <- sqlInterpolate(ANSI(),
    "SELECT n.nuc_sequence FROM nucleotide2amino na INNER JOIN nucleotide n ON
(na.locustranscript = n.locustranscript AND na.bjnumber = n.bjnumber) WHERE na.bjnumber = ?bjNum
and na.aanumber = ?aaNum;",
    bjNum = bjNum,
    aaNum = aaNum
  )
  outp5 <- dbGetQuery(pool, query2)
  query2 = NULL

  output$text5 <- renderText(selectedHit)
  output$text4 <- renderText(paste0('Protein Sequence:', '\n', amino_seq))
  output$text1 <- renderText(outp5[,1])

  # Generate Header for download fasta file
  seq_header <- paste0(outp3[index,3], ',aanum:', aaNum, ',bjnum:', bjNum, giID)
  giID = NULL

```

```

output$download <- downloadHandler(
  filename = function() {
    paste("Protein_Sequence-", Sys.Date(), ".fasta", sep="")
  },
  content = function(fname) {
    seqinr::write.fasta(as.list(amino_seq), names=seq_header, file=fname)
  }
)
output$download1 <- downloadHandler(
  filename = function() {
    paste("DNA_Sequence-", Sys.Date(), ".fasta", sep="")
  },
  content = function(fname) {
    seqinr::write.fasta(as.list(outp5[,1]), names=seq_header, file=fname)
  }
)
bjNum = NULL
aaNum = NULL

updateTabsetPanel(session, "main", selected = "Individual Sequences")
})
})
} else {
  # Code to apply filters for one or more Echino Species
  if(input$ASwitch == TRUE & input$CSwitch == TRUE & input$ESwitch == TRUE & input$HSwitch ==
TRUE & input$OSwitch == FALSE){
    spList <- c("Asteroidea", "Crinoidea", "Echinoidea", "Holothuroidea")
    sp_order <- c(input$Aoptions, input$Coptions, input$Eoptions, input$Hoptions)
  } else if (input$ASwitch == TRUE & input$CSwitch == TRUE & input$ESwitch == TRUE &
input$HSwitch == FALSE & input$OSwitch == TRUE){
    spList <- c("Asteroidea", "Crinoidea", "Echinoidea", "Ophiuroidea")
    sp_order <- c(input$Aoptions, input$Coptions, input$Eoptions, input$Ooptions)
  } else if (input$ASwitch == TRUE & input$CSwitch == TRUE & input$ESwitch == FALSE &
input$HSwitch == TRUE & input$OSwitch == TRUE){
    spList <- c("Asteroidea", "Crinoidea", "Holothuroidea", "Ophiuroidea")
    sp_order <- c(input$Aoptions, input$Coptions, input$Hoptions, input$Ooptions)
  } else if (input$ASwitch == TRUE & input$CSwitch == FALSE & input$ESwitch == TRUE &
input$HSwitch == TRUE & input$OSwitch == TRUE){
    spList <- c("Asteroidea", "Echinoidea", "Holothuroidea", "Ophiuroidea")
    sp_order <- c(input$Aoptions, input$Eoptions, input$Hoptions, input$Ooptions)
  } else if (input$ASwitch == FALSE & input$CSwitch == TRUE & input$ESwitch == TRUE &
input$HSwitch == TRUE & input$OSwitch == TRUE){
    spList <- c("Crinoidea", "Echinoidea", "Holothuroidea", "Ophiuroidea")
    sp_order <- c(input$Coptions, input$Eoptions, input$Hoptions, input$Ooptions)
  }

  else if (input$ASwitch == TRUE & input$CSwitch == TRUE & input$ESwitch == TRUE & input$HSwitch
== FALSE & input$OSwitch == FALSE){

```

```

    spList <- c("Asteroidea", "Crinoidea", "Echinoidea")
    sp_order <- c(input$Aoptions, input$Coptions, input$Eoptions)
  } else if (input$ASwitch == TRUE & input$CSwitch == TRUE & input$ESwitch == FALSE &
input$HSwitch == TRUE & input$OSwitch == FALSE){
    spList <- c("Asteroidea", "Crinoidea", "Holothuroidea")
    sp_order <- c(input$Aoptions, input$Coptions, input$Hoptions)
  } else if (input$ASwitch == TRUE & input$CSwitch == TRUE & input$ESwitch == FALSE &
input$HSwitch == FALSE & input$OSwitch == TRUE){
    spList <- c("Asteroidea", "Crinoidea", "Ophiuroidea")
    sp_order <- c(input$Aoptions, input$Coptions, input$Ooptions)
  } else if (input$ASwitch == TRUE & input$CSwitch == FALSE & input$ESwitch == TRUE &
input$HSwitch == TRUE & input$OSwitch == FALSE){
    spList <- c("Asteroidea", "Echinoidea", "Holothuroidea")
    sp_order <- c(input$Aoptions, input$Eoptions, input$Hoptions)
  } else if (input$ASwitch == TRUE & input$CSwitch == FALSE & input$ESwitch == TRUE &
input$HSwitch == FALSE & input$OSwitch == TRUE){
    spList <- c("Asteroidea", "Echinoidea", "Ophiuroidea")
    sp_order <- c(input$Aoptions, input$Eoptions, input$Ooptions)
  } else if (input$ASwitch == TRUE & input$CSwitch == FALSE & input$ESwitch == FALSE &
input$HSwitch == TRUE & input$OSwitch == TRUE){
    spList <- c("Asteroidea", "Holothuroidea", "Ophiuroidea")
    sp_order <- c(input$Aoptions, input$Hoptions, input$Ooptions)
  } else if (input$ASwitch == FALSE & input$CSwitch == TRUE & input$ESwitch == TRUE &
input$HSwitch == TRUE & input$OSwitch == FALSE){
    spList <- c("Crinoidea", "Echinoidea", "Holothuroidea")
    sp_order <- c(input$Coptions, input$Eoptions, input$Hoptions)
  } else if (input$ASwitch == FALSE & input$CSwitch == TRUE & input$ESwitch == TRUE &
input$HSwitch == FALSE & input$OSwitch == TRUE){
    spList <- c("Crinoidea", "Echinoidea", "Ophiuroidea")
    sp_order <- c(input$Coptions, input$Eoptions, input$Ooptions)
  } else if (input$ASwitch == FALSE & input$CSwitch == TRUE & input$ESwitch == FALSE &
input$HSwitch == TRUE & input$OSwitch == TRUE){
    spList <- c("Crinoidea", "Holothuroidea", "Ophiuroidea")
    sp_order <- c(input$Coptions, input$Hoptions, input$Ooptions)
  } else if (input$ASwitch == FALSE & input$CSwitch == FALSE & input$ESwitch == TRUE &
input$HSwitch == TRUE & input$OSwitch == TRUE){
    spList <- c("Echinoidea", "Holothuroidea", "Ophiuroidea")
    sp_order <- c(input$Eoptions, input$Hoptions, input$Ooptions)
  }
}

else if (input$ASwitch == TRUE & input$CSwitch == TRUE & input$ESwitch == FALSE &
input$HSwitch == FALSE & input$OSwitch == FALSE){
  spList <- c("Asteroidea", "Crinoidea")
  sp_order <- c(input$Aoptions, input$Coptions)
} else if (input$ASwitch == TRUE & input$CSwitch == FALSE & input$ESwitch == TRUE &
input$HSwitch == FALSE & input$OSwitch == FALSE){
  spList <- c("Asteroidea", "Echinoidea")
  sp_order <- c(input$Aoptions, input$Eoptions)
}

```

```

    } else if (input$ASwitch == TRUE & input$CSwitch == FALSE & input$ESwitch == FALSE &
input$HSwitch == TRUE & input$OSwitch == FALSE){
      spList <- c("Asteroidea", "Holothuroidea")
      sp_order <- c(input$Aoptions, input$Hoptions)
    } else if (input$ASwitch == TRUE & input$CSwitch == FALSE & input$ESwitch == FALSE &
input$HSwitch == FALSE & input$OSwitch == TRUE){
      spList <- c("Asteroidea", "Ophiuroidea")
      sp_order <- c(input$Aoptions, input$Ooptions)
    } else if (input$ASwitch == FALSE & input$CSwitch == TRUE & input$ESwitch == TRUE &
input$HSwitch == FALSE & input$OSwitch == FALSE){
      spList <- c("Crinoidea", "Echinoidea")
      sp_order <- c(input$Coptions, input$Eoptions)
    } else if (input$ASwitch == FALSE & input$CSwitch == TRUE & input$ESwitch == FALSE &
input$HSwitch == TRUE & input$OSwitch == FALSE){
      spList <- c("Crinoidea", "Holothuroidea")
      sp_order <- c(input$Coptions, input$Hoptions)
    } else if (input$ASwitch == FALSE & input$CSwitch == TRUE & input$ESwitch == FALSE &
input$HSwitch == FALSE & input$OSwitch == TRUE){
      spList <- c("Crinoidea", "Ophiuroidea")
      sp_order <- c(input$Coptions, input$Ooptions)
    } else if (input$ASwitch == FALSE & input$CSwitch == FALSE & input$ESwitch == TRUE &
input$HSwitch == TRUE & input$OSwitch == FALSE){
      spList <- c("Echinoidea", "Holothuroidea")
      sp_order <- c(input$Eoptions, input$Hoptions)
    } else if (input$ASwitch == FALSE & input$CSwitch == FALSE & input$ESwitch == TRUE &
input$HSwitch == FALSE & input$OSwitch == TRUE){
      spList <- c("Echinoidea", "Ophiuroidea")
      sp_order <- c(input$Eoptions, input$Ooptions)
    } else if (input$ASwitch == FALSE & input$CSwitch == FALSE & input$ESwitch == FALSE &
input$HSwitch == TRUE & input$OSwitch == TRUE){
      spList <- c("Holothuroidea", "Ophiuroidea")
      sp_order <- c(input$Hoptions, input$Ooptions)
    }
}

```

```

else if (input$ASwitch == TRUE & input$CSwitch == FALSE & input$ESwitch == FALSE &
input$HSwitch == FALSE & input$OSwitch == FALSE){
  spList <- c("Asteroidea")
  sp_order <- input$Aoptions
} else if (input$ASwitch == FALSE & input$CSwitch == TRUE & input$ESwitch == FALSE &
input$HSwitch == FALSE & input$OSwitch == FALSE){
  spList <- c("Crinoidea")
  sp_order <- input$Coptions
} else if (input$ASwitch == FALSE & input$CSwitch == FALSE & input$ESwitch == TRUE &
input$HSwitch == FALSE & input$OSwitch == FALSE){
  spList <- c("Echinoidea")
  sp_order <- input$Eoptions
} else if (input$ASwitch == FALSE & input$CSwitch == FALSE & input$ESwitch == FALSE &
input$HSwitch == TRUE & input$OSwitch == FALSE){

```

```

spList <- c("Holothuroidea")
sp_order <- input$Hoptions
} else {
spList <- c("Ophiuroidea")
sp_order <- input$Ooptions
}

sp_familyA = sp_familyC = sp_familyE = sp_familyH = sp_familyO = NULL
if(input$ASwitch == TRUE){
tmp = tmp1 = tmp2 = tmp3 = tmp4 = tmp5 = tmp6 = NULL
if('Brisingida' %in% input$Aoptions){
tmp = input$BriOptions
}
if('Forcipulatida' %in% input$Aoptions){
tmp1 = input$ForciOptions
}
if('Notomyotida' %in% input$Aoptions){
tmp2 = input$NotoOptions
}
if('Paxillosida' %in% input$Aoptions){
tmp3 = input$PaxOptions
}
if('Spinulosida' %in% input$Aoptions){
tmp4 = input$SriOptions
}
if('Valvatida' %in% input$Aoptions){
tmp5 = input$ValOptions
}
if('Velatida' %in% input$Aoptions){
tmp6 = input$VelOptions
}
sp_familyA = c(tmp, tmp1, tmp2, tmp3, tmp4, tmp5, tmp6)
tmp = tmp1 = tmp2 = tmp3 = tmp4 = tmp5 = tmp6 = NULL
}

if(input$CSwitch == TRUE){
tmp = tmp1 = NULL
if('Comatulida' %in% input$Coptions){
tmp = input$ComOptions
}
if('Hyocrinida' %in% input$Coptions){
tmp1 = input$HyoOptions
}
sp_familyC = c(tmp, tmp1)
tmp = tmp1 = NULL
}

if(input$ESwitch == TRUE){

```

```

tmp = tmp1 = tmp2 = tmp3 = NULL
if('Arbacioida' %in% input$Eoptions){
  tmp = input$ArbOptions
}
if('Cidaroida' %in% input$Eoptions){
  tmp1 = input$CidOptions
}
if('Clypeasteroida' %in% input$Eoptions){
  tmp2 = input$ClyOptions
}
if('Echinoida' %in% input$Eoptions){
  tmp3 = input$EchOptions
}
sp_familyE = c(tmp, tmp1, tmp2, tmp3)
tmp = tmp1 = tmp2 = tmp3 = NULL
}

if(input$Hswitch == TRUE){
  tmp = tmp1 = tmp2 = tmp3 = tmp4 = tmp5 = NULL
  if('Apodida' %in% input$Hoptions){
    tmp = input$ApoOptions
  }
  if('Aspidochirotida' %in% input$Hoptions){
    tmp1 = input$AspOptions
  }
  if('Dendrochirota' %in% input$Hoptions){
    tmp2 = input$DenOptions
  }
  if('Dendrochirotida' %in% input$Hoptions){
    tmp3 = input$DendOptions
  }
  if('Elasipodida' %in% input$Hoptions){
    tmp4 = input$ElasOptions
  }
  if('Molpadida' %in% input$Hoptions){
    tmp5 = input$MolOptions
  }
  sp_familyH = c(tmp, tmp1, tmp2, tmp3, tmp4, tmp5)
  tmp = tmp1 = tmp2 = tmp3 = tmp4 = tmp5 = NULL
}

if(input$OSwitch == TRUE){
  tmp = tmp1 = tmp2 = tmp3 = NULL
  if('Euryalida' %in% input$Ooptions){
    tmp = input$EurOptions
  }
  if('Gnathophiuridea' %in% input$Ooptions){
    tmp1 = input$GnaOptions
  }
}

```

```

}
if('Ophiocomidea' %in% input$Ooptions){
  tmp2 = input$OphiOptions
}
if('Ophiurida' %in% input$Ooptions){
  tmp3 = input$OphiOptions
}
sp_familyO = c(tmp, tmp1, tmp2, tmp3)
tmp = tmp1 = tmp2 = tmp3 = NULL
}

sp_family = c(sp_familyA, sp_familyC, sp_familyE, sp_familyH, sp_familyO)
# print(sp_family)

sp_familyA = sp_familyC = sp_familyE = sp_familyH = sp_familyO = NULL
# Convert array to a string
p_class <- paste(unlist(spList), collapse=', ')

if(length(sp_order) >= 1){
  p_order <- paste(unlist(sp_order), collapse=', ')
  if(length(sp_family) >= 1){
    p_family <- paste(unlist(sp_family), collapse=', ')
    # print(p_order)
    # print(p_family)
    qry1 <- pool %>% dbGetQuery(paste0("SELECT TESTDB_FUNC_SPECIES('{", p_class, "}', '{",
p_order, "}', '{", p_family, "}");"))
  } else {
    qry1 <- pool %>% dbGetQuery(paste0("SELECT TESTDB_FUNC_SPECIES('{", p_class, "}', '{",
p_order, "}', '{'}");"))
  }
} else {
  qry1 <- pool %>% dbGetQuery(paste0("SELECT TESTDB_FUNC_SPECIES('{", p_class, "}', '{', '{'}");"))
}

# Strip curly brackets off species function output
qr <- gsub("\\{\\|\\}", "", qry1)
# Convert string into array
qr = strsplit(qr, ",")[1]

# Query orthoclusters table based on bjnumber
qry = "SELECT gi_num FROM orthoclusters WHERE bjnumber IN ({out*});"
query_v <- glue::glue_sql(qry, out = qr, .con=pool)
outp_view <- dbGetQuery(pool, query_v)
# print(query_v)
qry = NULL
query_v = NULL

outp = subset(outp, outp[,1] %in% outp_view[,1])

```

```

v1 = outp[,1]
outp_view = NULL

sql <- "SELECT COUNT(*),gi_num FROM orthoclusters WHERE gi_num IN ({gi*}) AND bjnumber IN
({bj*}) GROUP BY gi_num;"
query <- glue::glue_sql(sql, gi = v1, bj=qr , .con=pool)
outp1 <- dbGetQuery(pool, query)
sql = NULL
query = NULL

# Remove entries from outp based on gi_num
ifelse(length(outp[,1]) == 0, outp,
  {
    outp <- as.data.frame(subset(outp, outp[,1] %in% outp1[,2]))

    # Sort outp and outp1 data by gi_num
    outp <- outp[order(outp$gi_num),]
    outp1 <- outp1[order(outp1[,2]),]

    # Create new column for total hits in outp dataframe
    outp$TotalHits <- outp1[,1]

    # Clear count data from ortholuster
    outp1 = NULL
    # names(outp)[names(outp) == "_searchtext"] <- "Refseq_Id"
    # outp[,4] <- apply(outp, 1, myfunc)
    names(outp)[names(outp) == "refnum"] <- "Accession#"
  })
output$text3 <- renderText(paste0(nrow(outp), " result(s) found"))

# Table on first page to display data from orthoclusters based on ginum and bjnum
output$table <- DT::renderDataTable( {
  as.datatable(
    selection = "single",
    style = 'bootstrap',
    formattable(outp, list(
      paging = FALSE,cyl = col_format(),
      `gi_num` = color_tile(customGreen, customGreen)
    )))
})

# If row is selected, navigate to Orthoclusters Tab
observeEvent(input$table_rows_selected, {
  shiny::withProgress(message='Please wait...',
    detail= 'Loading data',
    value = 0, {
      n <- 1
      for (i in 1:n) {

```

```

shiny::incProgress(amount=1/n)
selectedIndex <- input$table_rows_selected
selectedRow <- outp[selectedIndex,]
selectedGI <- selectedRow[1,]
selectedHit <- paste0('Orthocluster for ', selectedRow[4], ' (',
                      selectedGI, ')', '\n', selectedRow[2], '\n',
                      selectedRow[5], ' sequences in orthocluster')

sql = "SELECT aanumber, bjnumber, concat(bjnumber, ':', aanumber) AS aa_bjnum,
gi_num from orthoclusters WHERE gi_num IN ({gi*}) AND bjnumber IN ({bj*});"
query <- glue::glue_sql(sql, gi = selectedGI, bj=qr, .con=pool)
outp2 <- dbGetQuery(pool, query)
sql = NULL
query = NULL

aabj = outp2[,3]
sql1 <- "select aanumber, bjnumber, sp_name, bio_proj_accesion, amino_sequence
from TESTDB_VIEW where aa_bjnum IN ({aabj*});"
query3 <- glue::glue_sql(sql1, aabj= aabj, .con=pool)
outp3 <- dbGetQuery(pool, query3)
sql1 = NULL
query3 = NULL
aabj = NULL

# Generate Header for download orthocluster sequence
seqs_fasta <- outp3[,5]
giID <- paste0('id:', selectedGI, ', orthocluster:', selectedRow[4])
namesList <- apply(outp3, 1, concat)
names_fasta <- paste(namesList, rep(giID))
namesList = NULL

# Add space after 60 lines in a sequence
outp3[,5] <- gsub('(.{60})', '\\1 ', outp3[,5])

output$text2 <- renderText(selectedHit)
} # End of Progress Bar For Loop
})

output$table1 <- renderDataTable({
  expr = DT::datatable(outp3,
    selection="single",
    options = list(
      columnDefs = list(list(visible=FALSE, targets={1:2})))
  ) %>% formatStyle("amino_sequence", color = customBlue, fontWeight = 'bold')
})

output$download2 <- downloadHandler(
  filename = function() {

```

```

    paste("Ortho_Sequences-", Sys.Date(), ".fasta", sep="")
  },
  content = function(fname) {
    seqinr::write.fasta(as.list(seqs_fasta), names=names_fasta, file=fname)
  }
)
updateTabsetPanel(session, "main", selected = "Orthocluster")

# If row is selected, navigate to tab3
observeEvent(input$table1_rows_selected, {
  index <- input$table1_rows_selected
  aaNum = outp3[index,1]
  bjNum = outp3[index,2]
  amino_seq = gsub(" ", "", outp3[index,5])

  query2 <- sqlInterpolate(ANSI(),
    "SELECT n.nuc_sequence FROM nucleotide2amino na INNER JOIN nucleotide n ON
(na.locustranscript = n.locustranscript AND na.bjnumber = n.bjnumber) WHERE na.bjnumber = ?bjNum
and na.aanumber = ?aaNum;",
    bjNum = bjNum,
    aaNum = aaNum)
  outp5 <- dbGetQuery(pool, query2)
  query2 = NULL

  output$text5 <- renderText(selectedHit)
  output$text4 <- renderText(paste0('Protein Sequence:', '\n',amino_seq))
  output$text1 <- renderText(outp5[,1])

  # Generate Header for download fasta file
  seq_header <- paste0(outp3[index,3], ',aanum:', aaNum, ',bjnum:', bjNum, giID)
  giID = NULL

  output$download <- downloadHandler(
    filename = function() {
      paste("Protein_Sequence-", Sys.Date(), ".fasta", sep="")
    },
    content = function(fname) {
      seqinr::write.fasta(as.list(amino_seq), names=seq_header, file=fname)
    }
  )
  output$download1 <- downloadHandler(
    filename = function() {
      paste("DNA_Sequence-", Sys.Date(), ".fasta", sep="")
    },
    content = function(fname) {
      seqinr::write.fasta(as.list(outp5[,1]), names=seq_header, file=fname)
    }
  )
)

```

```

    bjNum = NULL
    aaNum = NULL

    updateTabsetPanel(session, "main", selected = "Individual Sequences")
  })

})
}

} else {
  outp <- NULL
  output$text3 <- renderText("No results to display...!!")
  updateTabItems(session, "main", "Results")
  output$table <- DT::renderDataTable(expr=NULL)
  output$table1 <- DT::renderDataTable(expr=NULL)
  output$table2 <- DT::renderDataTable(expr=NULL)
  output$text5 <- renderText("")
  output$text4 <- renderText("")
  output$text2 <- renderText("")
  output$text1 <- renderText("")
}
})
observeEvent(input$clearButton, {
  shinyjs::js$refresh()
  updateTextInput(session, "searchText", value="")
  updateTabItems(session, "main", "Results")
  updatePrettySwitch(session, inputId= "allSwitch", value = TRUE)
  output$table <- DT::renderDataTable(expr=NULL)
  output$table1 <- DT::renderDataTable(expr=NULL)
  output$table2 <- DT::renderDataTable(expr=NULL)
  output$text5 <- renderText("")
  output$text4 <- renderText("")
  output$text3 <- renderText("")
  output$text2 <- renderText("")
  output$text1 <- renderText("")
})

output$papersTable <- DT::renderDataTable({
  as.datatable(
    selection = "single",
    style = 'bootstrap',
    formattable(outLP1, list(
      paging = TRUE, cyl = col_format()
    )
  )
})

```

If row in papersTable is selected, Browse Literature Paper

```

observeEvent(input$papersTable_rows_selected, {
  ind = input$papersTable_rows_selected
  url = outLP[ind,2]
  # browseURL(url)
  js$browseURL(url)
})

#Link button to download Greg's Supplemental List Data
output$downloadFile <- downloadHandler(
  filename <- function() {
    paste("SupplementaryMaterials", "zip", sep=".")
  },
  content <- function(file) {
    file.copy("/home/ubuntu/EchinoManual/SupplementaryMaterials.zip", file)
  }
)

output$text6 <- renderText({ "Note: Please select document and press download button to save locally
in your downloads directory"})
output$docsTable <- DT::renderDataTable({
  shinyjs::disable("downloadDoc")
  as.datatable(
    selection = "single",
    style = 'bootstrap',
    options = list(dom = 't'),
    formattable(outLD1, list(
      paging=TRUE, cyl = col_format())
    )
  )
})
# If row in docsTable is selected, Download Documents
observeEvent(input$docsTable_rows_selected, {
  shinyjs::enable("downloadDoc")
  ind1 = input$docsTable_rows_selected
  fnameD = outLD[ind1,1]
  locD = outLD[ind1,2]
  extn = outLD[ind1, 3]
  contentTp = outLD[ind1, 4]
  print(locD)
  print(contentTp)
  output$downloadDoc <- downloadHandler(
    filename <- function() {
      paste(fnameD, extn, sep=".")
    },
    content <- function(file) {
      file.copy(locD, file)
    },
    contentType = contentTp
  )
}

```

```

)
})

col_format <- reactive({
  formatter("span",style = x ~ style(
    color = 'grey',font.weight = "bold"))
})

session$onSessionEnded(function() {
  pool::poolClose(pool)
})

}

# Run the application
shinyApp(ui = ui, server = server)

```

EchinoidDB code

```

# load the required packages
library(shiny)
library(shinydashboard)
library(RPostgreSQL)
library(pool)
library(DBI)
library(DT)
library(formattable)
library(shinyWidgets)
library(shinyjs)

setMethod("dbQuoteLiteral", c("Pool", "ANY"),
  function(conn, x, ...) {
    # As of 2020-05-07, this is necessary due to an incompatibility
    # between packages `pool` (v 0.1.4.3) and `glue` (v >= 1.3.2).
    connection <- pool::poolCheckout(conn)
    on.exit(pool::poolReturn(connection))
    DBI::dbQuoteLiteral(connection, x, ...)
  }
)

jrcode <- '$(document).keyup(function(e) {
  if (e.key == "Enter") {
    $('#searchButton').click();
  }});'

jsDeleteKey <- '$(document).keyup(function(e) {

```

```
if (e.key == "Delete") {
  $("#clearButton").click();
}});'
```

```
#Dashboard header carrying the title of the dashboard
header <- dashboardHeader(title = "EchinoidDB")
```

```
sidebar <- dashboardSidebar(
```

```
  #HTML CSS Scripts
```

```
  tags$head(tags$script(HTML(jscode))),
```

```
  tags$head(tags$script(HTML(jsDeleteKey))),
```

```
  tags$style(HTML('#searchText{color: #337ab7;border-color:orange; font-weight:bold;}')),
```

```
  tags$style(type="text/css", "#seqText {color: #006680;
```

```
    background-color:#FFFFFF; font-weight:bold; border-color:#006680;
```

```
    word-wrap: break-word; white-space: normal;}"
```

```
),
```

```
  tags$style(type="text/css", "#dnaSeq {height: 250px; color: #006680;
```

```
    background-color:#FFFFFF; font-weight:bold; border-color:#006680;
```

```
    word-wrap: break-word; white-space: normal;}"
```

```
),
```

```
  tags$style(type="text/css", "#descText{ background-color: #006680;
```

```
    color: #ffffff; word-wrap: break-word; display: inline-block;
```

```
    overflow-wrap: break-word; word-break: normal;
```

```
    line-break: strict; white-space: normal;
```

```
    font-family: Times New Roman;}"
```

```
),
```

```
  tags$style(type="text/css", "#infoText, #detailsText {color: #b20838;
```

```
    background-color:#FFFAFA; font-weight:bold; border-color:#FFFAFA;}"
```

```
),
```

```
  tags$style(type="text/css", "#detailsText1 {color: #006680;
```

```
    background-color:#FFFAFA; font-weight:bold; border-color:#FFFAFA;}"
```

```
),
```

```
  tags$style(type="text/css", "#downloadData{ font-weight:bold; color: #006680;
```

```
    font-family: Brush Script MT, monospace; float:right; padding: 9px;}"
```

```
),
```

```
  tags$style(type="text/css", "#dwnldResult, #dwnldDNA {color: #ffffff;
```

```
    background-color:#006680;float:right; font-family: Brush Script MT, monospace;}"),
```

```
#Fields in Sidebar Pane
```

```
textInput(inputId = "searchText",placeholder = "description, reference# etc.", label = "Enter Keyword  
& Hit Enter"),
```

```
actionButton(inputId = "searchButton", label="Submit Search",icon("search"),
```

```
  style="color: #fff; background-color: #a4163e; border-color:#a4163e;"),
```

```
actionButton(inputId = "clearButton", label="Clear", icon("backspace"),
```

```
  style="color: #ffffff; background-color: #006680;border-color:#006680;"),
```

```

sidebarMenu(
  menuItem("Link to Echino Dashboard", icon = icon("send"),
    href = "https://echinodb.uncc.edu"),
  menuItem("Link to Ophiuroid Dashboard", icon = icon("send"),
    href = "https://echinodb.uncc.edu/BStarApp/"),
  menuItem("Link to BLAST Server", icon = icon("send",lib='glyphicon'),
    href = "https://echinodb.uncc.edu/sequenceserver/")
)
)

frow <- fluidRow(
  downloadLink('downloadData',"Click to download Lytechinus variegatus Data"),
  box(solidHeader = FALSE, status = "danger", width = 12, collapsible = TRUE,
    tabsetPanel(id= "main",
      tabPanel("Results", br(), verbatimTextOutput("infoText"),
        DT::dataTableOutput("outpTable")),
      tabPanel("Sequences", br(), verbatimTextOutput("detailsText"),
        verbatimTextOutput("detailsText1"),
        downloadButton('dwnldResult',"Download Protein Sequence"), br(), br(),
          verbatimTextOutput("seqText"), downloadButton('dwnldDNA',"Download DNA
Sequence"),
          br(), br(), verbatimTextOutput("dnaSeq"))
    ),
    br(),
    verbatimTextOutput("descText"),
    uiOutput("images")
  )
)
# combine the two fluid rows to make the body
body <- dashboardBody(frow)

#completing the ui part with dashboardPage
ui <- dashboardPage(header, sidebar, body, skin='blue')

server <- function(input, output, session) {
  pool <- dbPool(
    drv = dbDriver("PostgreSQL", max.con = 100),
    dbname = "XXXXXX",
    host = "XXXXXXXX",
    user = "XXXXXXXX",
    password = "XXXXXXXX",
    idleTimeout = 3600000
  )
  output$descText <- renderText("A a high-quality, chromosomal-scale genome assembly
data of the Sea Urchin Lytechinus variegatus
(https://academic.oup.com/gbe/article/12/7/1080/5841217) is served here. The data can be searched
by keyword or downloaded from here."
)
}

```

```

output$images <- renderUI({
  tags$div(
    img(width= "80"),
    img(src='EchinolImages.PNG', width="800")
  )
})

observeEvent(input$searchButton, {
  req(input$searchText)
  sql <- "SELECT id, chromosome, startstop, ncbid, description FROM ly_variegatus WHERE (ncbid LIKE
?id) OR (description LIKE ?desc);"
  query <- sqlInterpolate(pool, sql, id = noquote(paste0('%', input$searchText, '%')),
    desc = noquote(paste0('%', input$searchText, '%')))
  outp <- dbGetQuery(pool, query)
  sql= NULL
  query = NULL

  if(length(outp) > 0){
    output$infoText <- renderText(paste0(nrow(outp), " result(s) found"))
    output$outpTable <- DT::renderDataTable({
      colnames(outp) <- c("Lytechinus variegatus ID", "ChrLoc", "Start-Stop", "Best BLAST Hit Used in
Annotation", "Best BLAST Hit Used in Description")
      as.datatable(
        selection = "single",
        style = 'bootstrap',
        formattable(outp, list(paging = TRUE))
      )
    })

    # If row is selected, navigate to Sequence Tab
    observeEvent(input$outpTable_rows_selected, {
      selectedIndex <- input$outpTable_rows_selected
      selectedRow <- outp[selectedIndex,]
      selectedID <- selectedRow[,1] #Selected ID
      selectedChr <- selectedRow[,2] #Selected Chromosome
      selectedSS <- selectedRow[,3] #Selected Sequence Start-Stop
      selectedRef <- selectedRow[,4] #Selected NCBI ID
      selectedDesc <- selectedRow[,5] #Selected Description

      query <- sqlInterpolate(ANSI(),
        "SELECT a.protseq, a.dnaseq, b.description FROM lva_nuclprot_seq AS a INNER JOIN
l_var_fasta_header AS b ON a.id = b.id WHERE a.id = ?id;", id = selectedID)
      outp1 <- dbGetQuery(pool, query)
      query <- NULL

      prothead = paste0(outp1[3])
      nuclheader = gsub("protein", "transcript", outp1[3])
    })
  }
})

```

```

#Header Text in Sequence Tab for BLAST Data
output$detailsText <- renderText(paste0(' BLAST Details-\n', '* ', selectedDesc, '\n',
'* Reference#: ', selectedRef, '\n',
'* chrLoc: ', selectedChr, '\n', '* sstart-stop: ', selectedSS))

output$detailsText1 <- renderText(paste0('Lytechinus variegatus ID: ', selectedID))
output$seqText <- renderText(paste0(outp1[,1])) #Resulting Protein Sequence

output$dnaSeq <- renderText(paste0(outp1[,2])) #Resulting Nucleotide Sequence

output$dwldResult <- downloadHandler(
  filename = function() {
    paste("LVA_Protein_Sequence_", Sys.Date(), ".fasta", sep="")
  },
  content = function(fname) {
    seqinr::write.fasta(outp1[,1], names=prothead, file=fname)
  }
)

output$dwldDNA <- downloadHandler(
  filename = function() {
    paste("LVA_DNA_Sequence_", Sys.Date(), ".fasta", sep="")
  },
  content = function(fname) {
    seqinr::write.fasta(outp1[,2], names=nucthead, file=fname)
  }
)

updateTabsetPanel(session, "main", selected = "Sequences")
})
else {
  output$infoText <- renderText("No results to display...!!")
  output$outpTable <- DT::renderDataTable(expr=NULL)
}
})

observeEvent(input$clearButton, {
  updateTextInput(session, "searchText", value="")
  updateTabItems(session, "main", "Results")
  output$seqText <- renderText("")
  output$infoText <- renderText("")
  output$detailsText <- renderText("")
  output$outpTable <- DT::renderDataTable(expr=NULL)
})

#Link button to download data

```

```

output$downloadData <- downloadHandler(
  filename <- function() {
    paste("Lytechinus_variegatus_SuppData", "zip", sep=".")
  },
  content <- function(file) {
    file.copy("/home/ubuntu/EchinoManual/WrayData.zip", file)
  }
)

session$onSessionEnded(function() {
  pool::poolClose(pool)
})
}
shinyApp(ui, server)

```

OphiuroidDB code

```

# load the required packages
library(shiny)
library(shinydashboard)
library(RPostgreSQL)
library(pool)
library(DBI)
library(DT)
library(formattable)
library(shinyWidgets)
library(shinyjs)

setMethod("dbQuoteLiteral", c("Pool", "ANY"),
  function(conn, x, ...) {
    # As of 2020-05-07, this is necessary due to an incompatibility
    # between packages `pool` (v 0.1.4.3) and `glue` (v >= 1.3.2).
    connection <- pool::poolCheckout(conn)
    on.exit(pool::poolReturn(connection))
    DBI::dbQuoteLiteral(connection, x, ...)
  }
)

jrcode <- '$(document).keyup(function(e) {
  if (e.key == "Enter") {
    $("#searchButton").click();
  }});'

jsDeleteKey <- '$(document).keyup(function(e) {
  if (e.key == "Delete") {
    $("#clearButton").click();
  }});'

```

```

#Dashboard header carrying the title of the dashboard
header <- dashboardHeader(title = "OphiuroidDB")
#Sidebar content of the dashboard
sidebar <- dashboardSidebar(
  #HTML CSS Scripts
  tags$head(tags$script(HTML(jscode))),
  tags$head(tags$script(HTML(jsDeleteKey))),
  tags$style(HTML('#searchText{color: #337ab7;border-color:orange; font-weight:bold;}')),

  tags$style(type="text/css", "#seqText { color: #006680;
    background-color:#FFFFFF; font-weight:bold; border-color:#006680;
    word-wrap: break-word; white-space: normal;}"),
  ),
  tags$style(type="text/css", "#descText{background-color: #006680;
    color: #ffffff; word-wrap: break-word; display: inline-block;
    overflow-wrap: break-word; word-break: normal;
    line-break: strict; white-space: normal;
    font-family: Times New Roman;}"),
  ),
  tags$style(type="text/css", "#infoText, #detailsText {color: #b20838;
    background-color:#FFFAFA; font-weight:bold; border-color:#FFFAFA;}"),
  ),
  tags$style(type="text/css", "#detailsText1 {color: #006680;
    background-color:#FFFAFA; font-weight:bold; border-color:#FFFAFA;}"),
  ),
  tags$style(type="text/css", "#downloadData{ font-weight:bold; color: #006680;
    font-family: Brush Script MT, monospace; float:right; padding: 9px;}"),
  ),
  tags$style(type="text/css", "#dwnldResult {color: #ffffff;
    background-color:#006680;float:right; font-family: Brush Script MT, monospace;}"),

#Fields in Sidebar Pane
textInput(inputId = "searchText",placeholder = "description, reference# etc.", label = "Enter Keyword
& Hit Enter"),
actionButton(inputId = "searchButton", label="Submit Search",icon("search"),
  style="color: #fff; background-color: #a4163e; border-color:#a4163e;"),
actionButton(inputId = "clearButton", label="Clear", icon("backspace"),
  style="color: #ffffff; background-color: #006680;border-color:#006680;"),
sidebarMenu(
  menuItem("Link to Echino Dashboard", icon = icon("send"),
    href = "https://echinodb.uncc.edu"),
    menuItem("Link to Echinoid Dashboard", icon = icon("send"),
    href = "https://echinodb.uncc.edu/SUrchinApp/"),
    menuItem("Link to BLAST Server", icon = icon("send",lib='glyphicon'),
    href = "https://echinodb.uncc.edu/sequenceserver/")
  )
)

```

```

frow <- fluidRow(
  downloadLink('downloadData','Click to download Ophioderma brevispinum data"),
  box(solidHeader = FALSE, status = "danger", width = 12, collapsible = TRUE,
    tabsetPanel(id= "main",
      tabPanel("Results", br(), verbatimTextOutput("infoText"),
        DT::dataTableOutput("outpTable")),
      tabPanel("Sequences", downloadButton('dwnlndResult',"Download Result Sequence"), br(), br(),
        verbatimTextOutput("detailsText"),
        verbatimTextOutput("detailsText1"),
        verbatimTextOutput("seqText"))
    ),
  br(),
  verbatimTextOutput("descText"),
  uiOutput("images")
)
)
# combine the two fluid rows to make the body
body <- dashboardBody(frow)

#completing the ui part with dashboardPage
ui <- dashboardPage(header, sidebar, body, skin='blue')

server <- function(input, output, session) {
  pool <- dbPool(
    drv = dbDriver("PostgreSQL", max.con = 100),
    dbname = "XXXXXX",
    host = "XXXXXXXX",
    user = "XXXXXXXX",
    password = "XXXXXXXX",
    idleTimeout = 3600000
  )
  output$descText <- renderText("Transcriptome data from Mashanov, Akiona, Khoury, Ferrier, Reid,
Machado, Zueva, and Janies. Active Notch signaling is required for arm regeneration in a brittle
star. PloS one 15, no. 5 (2020): e0232981. is served here. The data can be searched by keyword
based on annotation by similarity to the Strongylocentrotus purpuratus genome."
)
  output$images <- renderUI({
    tags$div(
      img(width= "320"),
      img(src='BStarImages.PNG', width="300")
    )
  })
  observeEvent(input$searchButton, {
    req(input$searchText)
    sql <- "SELECT accession, description, chrlocation, clusterid FROM ophiuroids WHERE (accession
LIKE ?rf) OR (description LIKE ?desc) ;"
    query <- sqlInterpolate(pool, sql, rf = noquote(paste0('%', input$searchText, '%')),
      desc = noquote(paste0('%', input$searchText, '%')))
  })
}

```

```

outp <- dbGetQuery(pool, query)
sql= NULL
query = NULL

if(length(outp) > 0){
  output$infoText <- renderText(paste0(nrow(outp), " result(s) found"))
  output$outpTable <- DT::renderDataTable({
    colnames(outp) <- c("Best BLAST Hit Used in Annotation", "Best BLAST Hit Used in Description",
"sseq-send", "Ophioderma brevispinum ClusterID")
    as.datatable(
      selection = "single",
      style = 'bootstrap',
      formattable(outp, list(paging = TRUE))
    )
  })

  # If row is selected, navigate to Sequence Tab
  observeEvent(input$outpTable_rows_selected, {
    selectedIndex <- input$outpTable_rows_selected
    selectedRow <- outp[selectedIndex,]
    selectedRef <- selectedRow[,1] #Selected RefNum
      selectedDesc <- selectedRow[,2] #Selected Row Description
    selectedChr <- selectedRow[,3] #Selected Chromosome Location
      selectedCID <- selectedRow[,4] #Selected Cluster ID

    query <- sqlInterpolate(ANSI(),
      "SELECT dnasequence FROM ophiuroids WHERE accession = ?rf AND chrlocation = ?chr AND
clusterid = ?cid;",
      rf = selectedRef, chr=selectedChr, cid=selectedCID)
    outp1 <- dbGetQuery(pool, query)
    query <- NULL

    # Store Sequence into a variable
    seq = outp1[1,1]

    fastaheader = paste0(selectedCID, ',sp=Ophioderma brevispinum')

    #Header Text in Sequence Tab for BLAST Data
    output$detailsText <- renderText(paste0(" BLAST Details-", '\n', '* ', selectedDesc,
'\n',
      '* Reference#: ', selectedRef, '\n', '* sstart-send: ', selectedChr))
    output$detailsText1 <- renderText(paste0('Ophioderma brevispinum ClusterID: ', selectedCID))

    output$seqText <- renderText(paste0(seq)) #Resulting Nucleotide or DNA Sequence

    output$dwnldResult <- downloadHandler(
      filename = function() {

```

```

        paste("Ophioderma brevispinum Sequence _ ", Sys.Date(), ".fasta",
sep="")
    },
    content = function(fname) {
        seqinr::write.fasta(seq, names=fastaheader, file=fname)
    }
)

    updateTabsetPanel(session, "main", selected = "Sequences")
})
}
else {
    output$infoText <- renderText("No results to display...!!")
    output$outpTable <- DT::renderDataTable(expr=NULL)
}
})

observeEvent(input$clearButton, {
    updateTextInput(session, "searchText", value="")
    updateTabItems(session, "main", "Results")
    output$seqText <- renderText("")
    output$infoText <- renderText("")
    output$detailsText <- renderText("")
    output$detailsText1 <- renderText("")
    output$outpTable <- DT::renderDataTable(expr=NULL)
})

#Link button to download transcriptome data
output$downloadData <- downloadHandler(
    filename <- function() {
        paste("Ophioderma Brevispinum Data", "txt", sep=".")
    },
    content <- function(file) {
        file.copy("/home/ubuntu/EchinoManual/Transcriptome_Data.txt", file)
    }
)

session$onSessionEnded(function() {
    pool::poolClose(pool)
})
}
shinyApp(ui, server)

```